

D5.2 FINAL EVALUATION REPORT

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

JOIN THE MISSION TO BE BETTER PREPARED FOR FUTURE CROSS-BORDER HEALTH THREATS

Representing 24 countries in Europe, UNITED4Surveillance gathers expertise in public health, clinical microbiology, epidemiology and data-science to support the strengthening of integrated surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control on national and European level

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1. Executive summary

Project overview: UNITED4Surveillance is a three-year Joint Action (JA) funded under EU4Health, running from January 2023 to June 2026 (following a six-month extension). Coordinated by RIVM (Netherlands), the JA brought together over 40 partners from 24 European countries to strengthen integrated infectious disease surveillance across four thematic areas: laboratory-based reporting (WP2/T1), outbreak and signal detection (WP2/T2), hospital surveillance (WP3), and One Health surveillance (WP4).

Evaluation scope: Work Package 5 (WP5, lead: CIPH, Croatia) applied a mixed-methods approach throughout the project, including six post-meeting surveys, two annual evaluation surveys, a focus group with Work Package Leaders (WPLs), structured WPL input at project end, and review of documents.

Process evaluation: Satisfaction across all evaluated meetings and workshops was consistently high, with average scores ranging from 3.8 to 5.0 on a 1-5 scale. A positive trend was observed over time, with General Assembly scores increasing from 4.27 (Zandvoort, 2024) to 4.55 (Closing Meeting, 2026). Annual surveys confirmed positive experiences overall; Year 1 produced slightly higher average scores than Year 2, reflecting mid-project communication challenges.

Output evaluation: Most planned deliverables and milestones were completed. WP1, WP2, WP6, and WP7 completed all deliverables as planned. WP3 and WP4 achieved most deliverables, with some pilots remaining at preparatory rather than fully operational stages due to legal, technical, and resource constraints. Approximately 75% of annual survey respondents expressed satisfaction with milestone achievement.

Outcome evaluation: The Closing Meeting survey (n=31, 17 countries) provided strong evidence of impact: 96.7% confirmed that UNITED4Surveillance had strengthened collaboration and exchange; 93.5% rated outputs as useful or very useful; and 90.3% indicated their institution was likely or very likely to continue using project results. Key outputs include the open-source Signal Detection Tool, Gen-EpiX platform, updated national data standards, hospital surveillance protocols, One Health legal framework, and the UNITED4Surveillance Roadmap.

Conclusions: UNITED4Surveillance successfully achieved its general and specific objectives. The JA delivered practical, open-source outputs, generated high participant satisfaction, built a strong European expert network, and created favourable conditions for sustainability. Legal uncertainty around GDPR, IT interoperability challenges, and fragmented funding remain persistent structural challenges requiring continued attention at EU and national level.

2. Description of task

Deliverable D5.2 - Final Evaluation Report - is defined in the Grant Agreement as: "Report summarising evaluation activities and final evaluation of JA as regards general and specific objectives through process, output and outcome indicators. Final Evaluation Report submitted." The deliverable is led by WP5 (Evaluation) with CIPH as the responsible partner. The original submission deadline was Month 36 (December 2025), following the project extension, this was revised to Month 42 (June 2026).

3. Description of work & main achievements

3.1 Background of the task

Evaluation is an important component of the UNITED4Surveillance Joint Action, providing a structured approach to assessing project implementation, achievements, and overall impact. Work Package 5 (Evaluation) supports all other Work Packages by monitoring progress, collecting feedback from participants, and assessing whether project objectives have been achieved. The final evaluation builds upon these

activities and brings together evidence collected throughout the entire project duration. The purpose of this task is to assess the implementation and results of UNITED4Surveillance, identify key achievements and challenges, evaluate the usefulness of project outputs, and capture lessons learned that may support future European initiatives in infectious disease surveillance.

3.2 Description of the work carried out

The evaluation of UNITED4Surveillance was guided by the Evaluation Plan (MS18, June 2023) and applied a mixed-methods approach covering three complementary dimensions: process evaluation, output evaluation, and outcome evaluation. Data collection was coordinated by WP5 (CIPH) and included the following methods:

Post-meeting surveys: Standardised online surveys (EuSurvey platform) distributed to all participants following each in-person meeting or workshop. Surveys assessed ten dimensions: achievement of meeting objectives, organisation, presentation quality, opportunities to participate, learning and exchange, representation of views, time for discussion, time for networking, stakeholder engagement, and usefulness for follow-up work. Each survey included Likert-scale items (1-5) and open-ended questions. (Annex 1.)

Annual evaluation surveys: Two broader surveys conducted at the end of Year 1 (Month 12, n=41, 17 countries) and Year 2 (Month 24, n=28, 19 countries). These assessed overall satisfaction, communication effectiveness, resource accessibility, training opportunities, workload alignment, learning and exchange, project adaptation, milestone achievement, timeline adherence, and feasibility of integration with national programmes. (Annex 2.)

Focus group with WP Leaders: A structured focus group was conducted with WP Leaders at the General Assembly in Zandvoort (March 2024). The ORID Discussion Method (Objective-Reflective-Interpretive-Decisional) was used to facilitate in-depth discussion of roles, challenges, achievements, and areas for improvement. Results were reported in Deliverable D5.1.

WP leader structured input: At project close, all WP leaders were invited to provide structured written input covering: implementation status, deliverable completion, barriers encountered, key outputs, outcomes, sustainability, and lessons learned. Input was received from WP1 (RIVM), WP2/T1 (SSI/RIVM), WP2/T2 (RKI), WP3 (THL/ISS), WP4 (FHI/RIVM), WP6 (RIVM/NVSC), and WP7 (NVSC).

Review of documents: Review of project deliverables, milestone reports, meeting documentation, dissemination materials, and sustainability plans throughout the project lifecycle.

Figure 1. Evaluation coverage across UNITED4Surveillance activities, showing the number of respondents (blue) and countries represented (orange) per activity. Country representation ranged from 11 (WP3 Workshop) to 19 (Evaluation Survey 2) across all activities.

Table 1. Overview of UNITED4Surveillance evaluation activities, including date, location, number of respondents, countries represented, and evaluation type. Activities comprised six post-meeting evaluations conducted between April 2023 and May 2026, and two annual online surveys administered in December 2023 and December 2024.

Activity	Date / Location	Respondents	Countries	Type
WP2/T1 Kick-off Workshop	26–27 Apr 2023, Copenhagen	21	14	Post-meeting
WP3 Workshop	22–23 May 2023, Rome	15	11	Post-meeting
WP2/T2 Outbreak Detection	30–31 May 2023, Berlin	16	12	Post-meeting
General Assembly – Zandvoort	11–12 Mar 2024, Zandvoort	29	18	Post-meeting
General Assembly – Utrecht	10–11 Jun 2025, Utrecht	29	16	Post-meeting
Closing Meeting	20–21 May 2026, Utrecht	31	17	Post-meeting
First Evaluation Survey (Year 1)	December 2023	41	17	Annual survey
Second Evaluation Survey (Year 2)	December 2024	28	19	Annual survey

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Process evaluation

Process evaluation assessed the day-to-day functioning of UNITED4Surveillance: how meetings were organised, how communication and collaboration worked, and whether participants were satisfied with project processes. Evidence was drawn from post-meeting surveys covering six workshops and meetings and two General Assemblies, as well as two annual evaluation surveys.

Post-Meeting and Workshop Evaluations

Six meetings and workshops were evaluated during the project. Across all dimensions, scores were consistently positive (range 3.8-5.0 on a 1-5 scale). Meeting organisation was the highest-rated dimension overall, with scores above 4.4 across all events. WP-specific technical workshops scored particularly highly for learning and experience exchange.

Figure 2. Average satisfaction scores (1–5) across five evaluation domains — meeting objectives, organisation, presentations, learning & exchange, and usefulness for work package — for each post-meeting evaluation conducted between April 2023 and May 2026.

Meeting objectives: Scores ranged from 3.94 (Outbreak Detection Workshop) to 4.61 (Closing Meeting). Both General Assemblies and the Closing Meeting scored above 4.2, indicating that project events were successfully structured around clearly communicated objectives.

Meeting organisation: Consistently the strongest dimension. All events scored above 4.4, with the Closing Meeting at 4.77 and the WP3 Workshop at 4.73.

Presentation quality: Ranged from 4.24 (GA Zandvoort) to 4.67 (WP2/T1 Workshop). Technical workshops tended to score higher than general assemblies, suggesting that focused, expert-to-expert content was highly valued.

Learning and experience exchange: Rated 4.25-5.0. WP-specific workshops with practical content scored highest. Country presentations and pilot discussions were frequently highlighted as valuable for understanding different approaches.

Networking: One of dimensions with the most variation (range 4.0-4.7). In-person attendance was linked to higher networking scores; hybrid meetings presented challenges for equitable participation. Participants requested more dedicated networking time.

Usefulness for follow-up work: Showed the widest variation (3.81-4.60). WP3 and WP2/T1 workshops scored highest, reflecting strong relevance to ongoing work. The Outbreak Detection Workshop scored lowest, reflecting early-stage uncertainty about tool scope.

Annual Evaluation Surveys

Two annual surveys were conducted: First Evaluation Survey (Month 12, n=41, 17 countries) and Second Evaluation Survey (Month 24, n=28, 19 countries). Both surveys covered ten dimensions of project experience.

Figure 3. Average scores (1–5) across ten evaluation domains from the First (Year 1, n=41) and Second (Year 2, n=28) Annual Evaluation Surveys. Scores were broadly comparable between the two years, with most domains showing a slight decline in Year 2.

Overall satisfaction: Year 1: 83% rated 4 or 5 (satisfied/very satisfied); Year 2: 82%. Scores were stable and high overall. Administrative burden of WP leadership was noted as a source of dissatisfaction for some respondents.

Communication: Year 1: 68% rated above average or excellent; Year 2: 64%. Both surveys identified room for improvement, particularly for listener countries who reported receiving fewer updates from WP2 and WP3. Communication challenges were most prominent in Year 1 and described as diminishing over time.

Resource accessibility: Year 1: 61% above average; Year 2: 61%. Access to the RIVM Microsoft Teams environment was frequently mentioned as problematic. Regular email communication of key documents was appreciated as a workaround.

Training and development: Year 1: 51% rated 4 or 5; Year 2: 29%. The lowest-rated dimension in both surveys. Respondents noted that knowledge gained was informal rather than structured training.

Milestone achievement: Year 1: 75.6% satisfied or very satisfied; Year 2: 75.0%. Stable, high satisfaction with project progress.

National integration feasibility: Year 1: 61% rated 4 or 5; Year 2: 79%. Notably improved in Year 2, reflecting growing confidence in merging JA outputs with national programmes. Several countries referenced direct grant applications as evidence of integration.

Focus Group with Work Package Leaders (Zandvoort, 2024)

A focus group was conducted with WP Leaders at the Zandvoort General Assembly using the ORID Discussion Method. Key themes that emerged are summarised below.

WPL roles evolved over time: WP Leaders described transitions from directive roles in the early phase to more facilitative and mediating roles as the JA matured, fostering partner autonomy.

Community building as a major achievement: Participants consistently highlighted the formation of a strong, multidisciplinary community across countries and sectors as among the most valuable outcomes.

Partner engagement challenges: Ensuring active participation from all partners was the most commonly cited challenge, particularly for listener countries.

Cross-WP communication needed improvement: WPLs identified limited visibility of activities in other WPs as a persistent challenge, with improvements suggested including webinars and shared updates.

Standardised platforms and templates: Participants called for more consistent use of collaborative platforms and document templates to reduce duplication and improve efficiency.

3.3.2 Output evaluation

Output evaluation assessed whether UNITED4Surveillance produced the planned deliverables and milestones within agreed timelines, and whether participants perceived these outputs as useful. Evidence was drawn from WP leader input, annual surveys, review of documents, and the Closing Meeting survey. Annual surveys confirmed that approximately 75% of respondents in both Year 1 and Year 2 were satisfied or very satisfied with milestone achievement and timeline adherence. Where delays occurred, they were primarily attributable to legal and administrative processes rather than technical failures or lack of effort.

Table 2. Overview of work package implementation status, including lead institutions, key deliverables, completion status, and extent of delays. Most work packages were fully completed with only minor delays.

WP	Lead	Key Deliverables	Completion	Delays
WP1 – Coordination	RIVM	D1.1 Progress Report, D1.2 Project Booklet	Yes	Minor–Moderate
WP2/T1 – Lab surveillance	SSI, RIVM	D2.1 Review, D2.2 Recommendations & training, 4 national pilots (DK, NL, FI, NO)	Yes	Minor
WP2/T2 – Outbreak detection	RKI	Open-source Signal Detection Tool, training materials, multi-country evaluation	Yes	Minor
WP3 – Hospital surveillance	THL, ISS	D3.1 MS Survey, D3.2 Recommendations & training, multi-country pilots	Mostly	Moderate
WP4 – One Health	FHI, RIVM	14 stakeholder analyses, 13 system mapping workshops, 12 country pilots (8 countries), 3 webinars on ECDC Learning Portal, scientific publications	Yes	Minor
WP5 – Evaluation	CIPH	D5.1 Evaluation Workshop Report, D5.2 Final Evaluation Report	Yes	Minor
WP6 – Dissemination	NVSC, RIVM	D6.1 Website, D6.2 Infographic, D6.3 MS Needs Assessment, D6.4 Final Report	Yes	Minor
WP7 – Sustainability	NVSC	D7.1–7.3 Sustainability Plans, UNITED4Surveillance Roadmap	Mostly	Minor

Signal Detection Tool (WP2/T2, RKI): An open-source, co-developed tool for automated outbreak detection, publicly available on [GitHub](#). The tool was piloted in ten countries; Further development and adoption of tool to national context is ongoing in Germany, Poland, Austria and other countries. Training package on automated signal detection and hands-on tool use was developed and incorporated into EPIET time-series analysis module

Gen-EpiX Genomic Epidemiology Platform (WP2/T1, NL): A country-specific, open-source platform for laboratory-based surveillance. Forms the basis of LabSentiNL, the Netherlands' new national surveillance infrastructure.

Updated National Data Transfer Protocols (WP2/T1, DK): Revised microbiology data exchange protocol (MedCom-approved, integrated into MiBa). Strengthened national surveillance of STEC (WP2/T1, FI & NO): Updated STEC data transfer standards integrated into national LIMS and national infectious disease register (NIDR). Harmonization of reporting practices between medical microbiology laboratories.

Hospital Surveillance Tools and Protocols (WP3): Across 10+ piloting countries: draft national protocols, electronic notification forms, data linkage approaches, stakeholder mapping, and automated reporting or visualization tools (Malta GI reports, Finland Shiny app, Latvia digital reporting forms).

One Health Surveillance Framework and Legal Analysis (WP4): Legal framework for One Health data sharing (NL); stakeholder analysis and system mapping for Salmonella and Campylobacter; scientific publications on WGS-based surveillance and SARI hospital surveillance.

UNITED4Surveillance Roadmap (WP7): An interactive roadmap supporting implementation of integrated infectious disease surveillance, covering lessons learned from all WPs and guidance for future action.

Initial Assessment of Member States Surveillance Systems (WP6): Public-domain overview of surveillance systems and needs across 24 EU/EEA countries, available on Zenodo and the UNITED4Surveillance website.

All UNITED4Surveillance deliverables are publicly available on the project website:
<https://united4surveillance.eu/project/results/>

3.3.3. Outcome Evaluation

Outcome evaluation assessed the broader effects of UNITED4Surveillance beyond the immediate delivery of outputs. Evidence was drawn primarily from the Closing Meeting survey (n=31, 17 countries) and WP-leaders structured input, supplemented by annual survey data and the focus group.

Figure 4. Outcome indicator ratings from the Closing Meeting (n=31, 17 countries), presented as percentage of respondents across three response categories (scores 3–5). Positive ratings (scores 4–5) were high across all three domains.

Strengthened collaboration and exchange: 96.7% of Closing Meeting respondents confirmed that UNITED4Surveillance had strengthened collaboration and exchange between participating countries and institutions (41.9% "very high", 54.8% "high"). This was the most consistently reported outcome, confirmed by annual surveys, focus group, and WP leader input. The JA created and sustained a multidisciplinary network spanning public health, microbiology, epidemiology, data science, and clinical medicine across 24 countries.

Usefulness of outputs and deliverables: 93.5% of respondents considered project outputs useful or very useful for their institution or country (51.6% "very useful", 41.9% "useful"). The Signal Detection Tool was most frequently named as the most valuable achievement by Closing Meeting respondents, followed by the Roadmap, networking and sharing of experiences, and specific national laboratory surveillance improvements.

Sustainability and continued use: 90.3% indicated their institution was likely or very likely to continue using or building upon outputs (41.9% "very likely", 48.4% "likely"). WP-leader input confirmed concrete sustainability pathways through direct grant applications, national programme integration, and continuation of established expert networks.

Capacity building and knowledge exchange: Annual surveys and the focus group confirmed that UNITED4Surveillance functioned as a significant platform for learning. Participants gained knowledge of surveillance approaches in other countries, built inter-institutional relationships, and developed practical skills in genomic epidemiology, outbreak detection algorithms, and hospital surveillance system design. Structured learning was further supported through dedicated training materials developed across work packages: a training package on automated signal detection and hands-on tool use, incorporated into the EPIET time-series analysis module (WP2/T2); a 50-minute webinar on hospital surveillance addressing common obstacles, legal issues, and data integration (WP3); and three webinars on zoonotic influenza, vector-borne diseases, and foodborne diseases, all hosted on the ECDC Learning Portal (WP4).

Policy impact: The legal analysis produced by WP2/T1 on **legal** barriers to laboratory data sharing was presented to DG SANTE and ECDC and contributed to the framing of the EU4H-2023-DGA-MS3-IBA direct grant call. Dutch Public Health Act amendments addressing data sharing are in process. JA findings were presented to ECDC during a dedicated site visit to the Steering Committee (January 2025).

Sustainability pathways

Table 3. Examples of national sustainability pathways for key UNITED4Surveillance outputs and tools, by country and work package.

Country / WP	Output / Tool	Sustainability pathway
Netherlands (WP2/T1, WP4)	Gen-EpiX / LabSentiNL, OH legal framework	Direct Grant Surveillance4NL; potential ALL4OneHealth grant
Germany (WP2/T2)	Signal Detection Tool	TICSID national direct grant; further development of tool and adoption to national and regional context
Denmark (WP2/T1)	MiBa data transfer protocol	MedCom-certified standard; integrated into national systems and will remain in use; will keep building on the output developed under UNITED4Surveillance in the EU-co-funded direct grant UpSurvDK
Finland (WP2/T1, WP3)	STEC data model, register-based SARI tools	Integrated into national LIMS and NIDR; national surveillance plans
Poland (WP2/T2)	Signal Detection Tool	National direct grant PNEWRS – integration into surveillance system
Multiple countries (WP3)	Hospital surveillance protocols and frameworks	National surveillance plans; direct grants; legislative reform
Denmark (WP4)	Materials developed for piloting active zoonotic influenza surveillance in humans	Materials developed under UNITED4Surveillance have been adapted for further use in the EU-co-funded direct grant UpSurvDK.
All partners (WP7)	UNITED4Surveillance Roadmap	Public document; national sustainability plans; used in follow-up initiatives

3.3.4 Results by Work Package

This section summarises the assessment of each work package against its specific objectives, drawing on WP leader input, deliverable review, and survey data.

WP1 - Project Coordination (RIVM)

All WP1 deliverables were completed or are on track within the extended timeline. D1.1 Progress Report was submitted; D1.2 Project Booklet is in progress. The Steering Committee met regularly, supported consortium agreement negotiations, and managed reporting to HaDEA. Delays were mainly attributable to HaDEA's amendment bundling requirement. Stakeholder engagement (ECDC site visits, DG SANTE presentations) was a notable strength. Key lesson: continuous consortium maintenance requires significant dedicated coordination effort in large multi-partner JAs.

WP2/T1 - Laboratory-Based Surveillance (SSI, RIVM)

All deliverables completed; objectives fully achieved. Four countries (DK, NL, FI, NO) completed national pilot projects. A needs and gaps analysis with 92% response rate identified legal barriers as the primary challenge. The Gen-EpiX platform (NL) and revised MiBa data transfer protocol (DK) are among the most concrete, sustained outputs. Legal analysis was shared with DG SANTE and contributed to future EU funding call. Key lesson: standardisation of data exchange formats and resolution of legal ambiguities require European-level action.

WP2/T2 - Outbreak & Signal Detection (RKI)

All deliverables completed; Objectives fully achieved. An open-source Signal Detection Tool was co-developed through a collaborative GitHub-based process. The tool was piloted in ten countries, and accompanied by SOPs and training materials. The tool is now integrated into national direct grant projects in Germany and Poland. GDPR-related data sharing constraints were the main technical barrier in early phases. Key lesson: co-development with active user feedback accelerates acceptance; IT support is essential for tool adoption.

WP3 - Hospital Surveillance (THL, ISS)

Most deliverables completed; objective achievement rated "mostly". Multiple piloting countries produced protocols, data linkage approaches, electronic notification tools, and analytical applications. Full automation and system-to-system integration was not realised within the project timeframe due to legal gaps, IT fragmentation, and resource constraints - structural challenges requiring sustained national investment. Key lesson: piloting is valuable but insufficient; legal frameworks and IT modernisation are preconditions for scaled hospital surveillance.

WP4 - One Health Surveillance (FHI, RIVM)

Objectives fully achieved. All planned stakeholder analyses (14), system mapping workshops (13), and country-level pilots (12 across 8 countries) were completed as planned. Piloting countries were Austria (Francisella tularensis, avian and swine influenza), Belgium (Salmonella, avian influenza), Denmark (STEC, avian and swine influenza), Italy (STEC), Lithuania (foodborne and tick-borne diseases), Netherlands (Salmonella), Norway (swine influenza), and Spain (West Nile Virus). Key outputs include standardised case questionnaires, integrated WGS data platforms for Salmonella and STEC, outbreak protocols, vector surveillance systems, and three training webinars hosted on the ECDC Learning Portal. Several country pilots led to peer-reviewed scientific publications. A key strength was the establishment of effective cross-sectoral collaboration platforms that built trust and enabled co-development of practical solutions across human, animal, and environmental health sectors. Main challenges included legal and ethical barriers to sampling (particularly for zoonotic influenza in farmers), uncertainty around implications of positive test results for livestock, and difficulties obtaining veterinary industry data due to client confidentiality concerns. Key lesson:

strong cross-sector collaboration, transparent data-sharing frameworks, and flexibility to adapt strategies (e.g., shifting between human and animal surveillance focus) are essential. Investment in WGS and digital infrastructure significantly enhanced outbreak detection, but requires continuous training and stakeholder commitment to sustain.

WP5 - Evaluation (CIPH)

All evaluation activities completed as planned. Evaluation plan, two annual surveys, focus group, data collection report, and final evaluation report were produced. Survey instruments were refined based on external evaluator feedback. Evaluation findings were regularly shared with the Steering Committee. This report (D5.2) finalises the evaluation cycle.

WP6 - Dissemination (NVSC, RIVM)

All deliverables completed. The UNITED4Surveillance website, infographic, and initial MS needs assessment were produced. Partners contributed actively through institutional channels. The website will remain active through the Direct Grant period (until 2029). Key lesson: timely communication from partners to the WP lead is critical for effective consortium-wide dissemination.

WP7 - Sustainability (NVSC)

Most deliverables completed; the UNITED4Surveillance Roadmap and national sustainability plans were developed. The Roadmap is publicly available and provides guidance for continued implementation. D7.3 Final Roadmap Report is in progress. Key lesson: sustainability requires active maintenance of networks and continued political commitment beyond project funding cycles.

3.3.5. SWOT analysis

The SWOT analysis synthesises findings from surveys, focus group discussions, WP leader input, and review of documents.

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong multi-country collaboration (40+ partners, 24 countries) • High stakeholder engagement and active community building • High overall participant satisfaction (avg. 4.0+ in most dimensions) • Practical, open-source outputs (Signal Detection Tool, Gen-EpiX) • Multidisciplinary and One Health approach • Established European expert network • Policy impact through DG SANTE engagement • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication challenges for listener/passive countries • Uneven engagement between piloting and non-piloting partners • Limited structured training opportunities • Cross-WP visibility and information sharing insufficient • Administrative burden high for WP leaders • Delays due to legal approvals and HaDEA amendment bundling • Technical challenges with Teams environment • Variation in digital maturity across countries
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Health Data Space (EHDS) supports data sharing • EU4H Direct Grant calls as sustainability pathway • Regulation (EU) 2022/2371 mandates molecular data sharing • Increasing national investment in surveillance digitalisation • Expansion of piloting activities under national direct grants • Stronger ECDC involvement in supporting national systems • Growing awareness of integrated One Health surveillance at EU level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR interpretation differences remain unresolved across Member States • Long-term funding uncertainties for surveillance infrastructure • Workforce shortages in public health and bioinformatics • Persistent interoperability challenges between national IT systems • Fragmented surveillance infrastructures difficult to modernise • Reduced engagement after project completion without dedicated funding • Budget pressures reducing national public health institute capacity • Proliferation of parallel EU initiatives creating coordination challenges

The SWOT analysis confirms that the main strengths of UNITED4Surveillance were its strong collaborative network, multidisciplinary approach, stakeholder engagement, and development of practical surveillance tools. The most frequently identified weaknesses and threats were related to legal barriers, data sharing challenges, and uncertainties regarding long-term funding. At the same time, opportunities arising from future European initiatives, including the European Health Data Space and follow-up projects, provide favourable conditions for further development and sustainability of project results.

3.4 Evaluation and conclusions

The evaluation findings indicate that UNITED4Surveillance successfully achieved its overall objectives and generated substantial added value for participating countries and institutions. Overall, the Joint Action was implemented successfully, with most planned activities, deliverables, milestones, and pilot projects completed as intended. Evaluation results demonstrated high levels of participant satisfaction, particularly regarding project meetings, opportunities for collaboration, and knowledge exchange. One of the main achievements of UNITED4Surveillance was the strengthening of collaboration between Member States and institutions involved in infectious disease surveillance. The project created valuable opportunities for networking, exchange of experiences, and multidisciplinary cooperation across public health, laboratory, hospital, and One Health sectors. The Joint Action also contributed to capacity building and supported the development of practical outputs, including surveillance tools, pilot activities, recommendations, training materials, sustainability plans, and the UNITED4Surveillance Roadmap. Several outputs have already been integrated into national activities or are expected to support future surveillance developments. The evaluation identified legal and regulatory barriers related to data sharing and GDPR interpretation as the most common challenge across Work Packages. Additional challenges included interoperability issues, limited human resources, and uncertainties regarding long-term funding of some initiatives. However, these challenges did not significantly affect the overall achievement of project objectives. Findings from the Closing Meeting survey further demonstrated that participants considered project outputs useful and reported a high likelihood of continuing to use or build upon the tools, outputs, and collaborations established through UNITED4Surveillance.

In conclusion, UNITED4Surveillance successfully strengthened collaboration, improved knowledge exchange, supported surveillance innovation, and established a strong foundation for future integrated infectious disease surveillance activities in Europe. The sustainability plans, Roadmap, and continued collaboration among participating organisations provide favourable conditions for maintaining and further developing the project's achievements beyond its formal duration.

4. Deviations from the work plan

A deviation from the original work plan occurred regarding the submission timeline of Deliverable D5.2 Final Evaluation Report. According to the initial project plan, the deliverable was scheduled for submission in Month 36. However, following the approval of a six-month extension of the UNITED4Surveillance project, the submission deadline for D5.2 was correspondingly extended by six months to align with the revised project timeline.

5. Performance of the partners

Most partner institutions contributed actively to the work carried out under WP5. Work Package Leaders from all work packages (WP1, WP2/T1, WP2/T2, WP3, WP4, WP6, and WP7) provided structured input for the final evaluation in a timely manner, enabling a comprehensive assessment of project implementation, outputs, and outcomes. Survey response rates varied across evaluation activities, which is typical for large multi-partner consortia. No partners failed to contribute or contributed in a significantly delayed or incomplete manner.

6. List of abbreviations/glossary

CIPH	Croatian Institute of Public Health
DG SANTE	European Commission Directorate-General for Health & Food Safety
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Gen-EpiX	Genomic Epidemiology platform for disease X
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HL7-FHIR	Health Level 7 – Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
ISS	Istituto Superiore di Sanità (Italy)
JA	Joint Action
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
MiBa	Danish National Microbiology Database
MS	Member State(s)
NIDR	National Infectious Disease Register (Finland)
NVSC	National Public Health Centre (Lithuania)
OH	One Health
ORID	Objective, Reflective, Interpretive, Decisional (discussion method)
RKI	Robert Koch Institute (Germany)
RIVM	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (Netherlands)
SARI	Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SC	Steering Committee
SSI	Statens Serum Institut (Denmark)
STEC	Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
UNITED4Surveillance / U4S	Union and National Capacity Building 4 IntegraTED Surveillance

WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Annex 1. Example of online survey – Evaluation of meetings

Draft ID: c0f66a67-8d77-4147-a7a2-3eb5de54a688 Date: 29/05/2023 12:32:15

UNITED4Surveillance Evaluation Form

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Name of workshop: _____

Date: _____

Place: _____

Dear Colleague, We invite you to take part in the evaluation of this meeting/workshop.

Your feedback is very valuable in view of future meetings and in view of the progress this project is making. All data will be treated confidentially and will only be reported in a general way with no attribution of responses to individuals.

Please indicate the context and country you work in.

I work in:

- Ministry of health or research
- National public health institute
- Local or regional public health authority
- Statistics office
- University
- International organization
- Other

If Other, please describe which:

The country I work in is:

- AT – Austria
- BE – Belgium
- CY – Cyprus
- CZ – Czech Republic
- DE – Germany
- DK – Denmark
- EE – Estonia
- ES – Spain
- FI – Finland
- FR – France
- HR – Croatia
- HU – Hungary
- IE – Ireland
- IT – Italy
- LT – Lithuania
- LU – Luxembourg
- LV – Latvia
- MT – Malta
- NL – Netherlands

- NO – Norway
- PL – Poland
- PT – Portugal
- RO – Romania
- SE – Sweden
- SI – Slovenia

How did you attend this workshop?

- In person
- Online

Please rate your satisfaction on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the least satisfied and 5 the most satisfied.

Reaching the objectives of the meeting

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Meeting organization

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

The content of presentations

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Opportunities to participate and contribute to the meeting

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Opportunities for learning and exchange of experiences

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Representations of different views (were the viewpoints of various stakeholders adequately represented)?

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Allocation of time for discussion

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Allocation of time for networking

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Engagement of all stakeholders

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

How satisfied are you with the usefulness of the meeting in terms of the follow-up work/tasks in the WP?

	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Comments and suggestions for future improvement:

Thank you for your participation!

Annex 2. Example of online survey - Annual evaluation surveys

Draft ID: 07ffba81-1028-4e36-96fb-c5c50cfed67b

Date: 29/06/2026 10:52:09

UNITED4Surveillance Evaluation Form

*Fields marked with * are mandatory.*

Dear Colleague,

We invite you to take part in the First Evaluation Survey.

Your feedback is very valuable in view of future meetings and in view of the progress this project is making.

All data will be treated confidentially and will only be reported in a general way with no attribution of responses to individuals.

Please indicate the context and country you work in.

*** I work in:**

- Ministry of health
- National public health authority
- Local or regional public health authority
- Statistics office
- University
- International organization
- Other

*** The country I work in is**

- AT – Austria
- BE – Belgium
- CZ – Czech Republic
- DE – Germany
- DK – Denmark
- EE – Estonia
- ES – Spain
- FI – Finland
- FR – France
- HR – Croatia
- HU – Hungary
- IE – Ireland
- IT – Italy
- LT – Lithuania
- LU – Luxembourg
- LV – Latvia
- MT – Malta
- NL – Netherlands
- NO – Norway
- PL – Poland
- PT – Portugal
- RO – Romania
- SE – Sweden
- SI – Slovenia

*** How would you rate your overall satisfaction with your experience as a participant in JA United4Surveillance over the past year?**

- 1 - Not satisfied
- 2 - Somewhat satisfied
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Satisfied
- 5 - Very satisfied

Additional Comments:

*** How would you rate the effectiveness of communication within the project, including updates, announcements, and feedback mechanisms?**

- 1 - Poor (Significant issues with communication, updates, and feedback)
- 2 - Below Average (Limited effectiveness, unclear updates, and weak feedback)
- 3 - Average (Basic communication with room for improvement)
- 4 - Above Average (Good communication, clear updates, and satisfactory feedback)
- 5 - Excellent (Highly effective communication, timely updates, and satisfactory feedback)

Additional Comments:

*** How would you rate the accessibility of resources (information, tools, guidelines) provided to you during your involvement in JA United4Surveillance?**

- 1 - Inadequate (Limited access to resources, insufficient information)
- 2 - Below Average (Some access, but resources are lacking or unclear)
- 3 - Average (Basic access to resources, with room for improvement)
- 4 - Above Average (Good access to resources, generally sufficient)
- 5 - Excellent (Highly accessible resources, comprehensive information and tools)

Additional Comments:

*** How satisfied are you with the training and development opportunities you've received for your role at JA United4Surveillance?**

- 1 - Not satisfied
- 2 - Somewhat satisfied
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Satisfied
- 5 - Very satisfied

If not, what improvements would you suggest?

*** On a scale from 1 to 5, to what extent did the time commitment for your participation align with your initial expectations upon joining the project?**

- 1 - Misaligned (Significant deviation from initial expectations)
- 2 - Below Expectations (Time commitment somewhat below expectations)
- 3 - As Expected (Reasonably aligned with initial expectations)
- 4 - Above Expectations (Time commitment somewhat above expectations)
- 5 - Exceeded Expectations (Significantly more time commitment than expected)

If there was a disparity, please share your thoughts on potential improvements

*** How would you describe the opportunities provided for learning and the exchange of experiences within JA United4Surveillance?**

- 1 - Inadequate (Limited learning opportunities, minimal experience exchange)
- 2 - Below Average (Some learning opportunities, moderate experience exchange)
- 3 - Average (Basic learning opportunities, occasional experience exchange)
- 4 - Above Average (Good learning opportunities, frequent experience exchange)
- 5 - Excellent (Abundant learning opportunities, extensive and valuable experience exchange)

Additional Comments:

*** How well do you think Project United4Surveillance has adapted to changes or challenges that have arisen during the past year?**

- 1 - Poor (Inadequate adaptation, significant challenges not addressed)
- 2 - Below Average (Limited adaptation, some challenges addressed)
- 3 - Average (Basic adaptation with room for improvement)
- 4 - Above Average (Good adaptation, most challenges addressed)
- 5 - Excellent (Highly effective adaptation, successfully navigated all challenges)

Additional Comments:

*** Are you satisfied with the achievement of project milestones and goals over the past year?**

- 1 - Not satisfied
- 2 - Somewhat satisfied
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Satisfied
- 5 - Very satisfied

If not, what specific areas do you believe need improvement?

*** How well has the project adhered to the initially set timelines and deadlines?**

- 1 - Poor (Significant delays and missed deadlines)
- 2 - Below Average (Some delays and difficulties meeting deadlines)
- 3 - Average (Met most deadlines with occasional delays)
- 4 - Above Average (Generally adhered to timelines with minor delays)
- 5 - Excellent (Consistently met or exceeded all timelines and deadlines)

Additional Comments:

*** If there were deviations, were they communicated effectively?**

- 1 - Inadequate (Deviations poorly communicated, lack of transparency)
- 2 - Below Average (Limited communication of deviations, some transparency issues)
- 3 - Average (Basic communication with room for improvement in transparency)
- 4 - Above Average (Deviation communication was generally effective)
- 5 - Excellent (Deviations communicated exceptionally well, high transparency)
- There were no deviations

Additional Comments:

*** On a scale of 1 to 5, how feasible do you believe it is to merge the work of JA United4Surveillance with ongoing national projects/programs that share similar objectives?**

- 1 - Not Feasible (Strong barriers or challenges to integration)
- 2 - Somewhat Feasible (Feasible with moderate challenges)
- 3 - Neutral (Mixed feasibility with both advantages and challenges)
- 4 - Feasible (Integration is likely with minor challenges)
- 5 - Highly Feasible (Integration is seamless with significant benefits)

Additional Comments:

What specific changes or improvements would you recommend to enhance the overall experience and effectiveness of JA United4Surveillance moving forward?

Thank you for your participation!